

Workshop - Supercharging Your Engineering Classes with Ethics!

Shannon Chance^{1,2}

¹ TU Dublin, Ireland

² University College London, UK

Email: shannon.chance@tudublin.ie

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Abstract

Are you ready to energize your students' learning of engineering ethics? Join us for a high-voltage, interactive workshop where we'll unlock the power of the **Routledge International Handbook of Engineering Ethics Education**—an open-source treasure trove of cutting-edge knowledge and active learning strategies! This dynamic workshop is designed for educators who want to infuse their courses with innovative, discipline-specific ethics learning methods. Through gamified exploration, creative brainstorming, and collaborative problem-solving, you'll walk away with practical strategies to integrate ethics into any engineering course. We'll kick things off with a dynamic guided tour of the handbook, unveiling its structure and offerings. Then, we'll divide into small teams for a high-energy brainstorming game to connect ethics education with various engineering topics using active learning pedagogies. Each team will get a custom "**Engineering Ethics Education Bingo 1.0**" card, and the first team to complete a row and defend their ideas wins bragging rights as Ethics Bingo Champions! Then, we'll gear down and give some thoughtful consideration to designing curricula to implement when we get home.

Keywords: Engineering Ethics Education; Active Learning; Teaching Methods; Ethics.

1 Introduction

This workshop will familiarize engineering educators with the content of *The Routledge International Handbook of Engineering Ethics Education* (Chance, Børsen et al., 2025), an open-source compendium of state-of-the-art knowledge and practice and help them apply the themes from the book. The 90-minute workshop adopts an active learning format inspired by events at the 2024 International Conference in Active Learning in Engineering Education. The workshop features active learning and project-learning approaches in engineering education, with a focus on integrating ethics using case studies (Herzog et al., 2025), problems via challenges and problem-based learning (Routhe et al., 2025), value-sensitive design (Gammon et al., 2025), service learning and humanitarian engineering (Daniel et al., 2025), arts-based methods (Hitt et al., 2025), and reflective approaches and dialogical approaches (Marin et al., 2025). Our motivation is to:

- celebrate the handbook,
- help educators know where to find it, what's in it, and how to use it,
- help them envision applying ethics-based activities into the modules they teach, and
- model the application of active learning approaches so they experience both fast and slow thinking.

The workshop will implement and further test a new game for learning about ethics in various engineering disciplines (we hope to present that tool as a paper at this same conference and then demonstrate its implementation as one part of this hands-on workshop). The workshop relates directly to the following conference themes:

- Inclusion, diversity, and ethics in Engineering Education
- Active Learning and PBL Approaches
- Education for sustainability
- Curriculum design
- Teacher's Professional Development for Active Learning

2 Activities

This workshop will involve the following activities:

- 1) A brief introduction to the handbook with quick identification of the six sections/thematic areas of the book and note of the active teaching methods and specific disciplines featured (10 minutes).
- 2) A fast-paced brainstorming activity called "Engineering Ethics Education (EEE) Bingo 1.0" (Chance, Murphy, Leão, Tobosaru, & Nolan, in review) in groups of 3-4 (35 minutes).
- 3) A whole-group recap on the Bingo game, collecting recommendations for improvement (10 minutes).
- 4) A more deliberative activity in which groups develop one specific idea (generated from, during, or following the Bingo game) into a specific plan for how to implement it in the courses they teach (30 minutes).
- 5) Wrap-up synthesizing discussion (5 minutes).

Figure 1. Pilot testing an earlier version of the bingo card at the 2025 SEFI Ethics Spring Symposium in Ireland.

3 Expected results

This submission should clearly state what the participants will achieve and/or deliver at the end of the workshop. This is not necessarily a concrete product but could also be the outcomes of a discussion.

By the end of this workshop, participants will be able to:

- name some topics covered in *The Routledge International Handbook of Engineering Ethics Education*,
- access the open-source book online.
- work in a small group to establish relationships between assignment/activity ideas, ethics topics, discipline areas, and teaching methods.
- develop ideas for applying ethics topics, discipline areas, and teaching methods in their classrooms.

4 Conclusions

In conclusion, the workshop will open with an overview of the handbook (explaining its structure, purpose, and content), assembling small teams for a group brainstorming game using a bingo card, and then zooming in to apply methods explored in the handbook for embedding ethics education via active learning approaches (case studies, project- and challenge-based learning, value-sensitive design, service- and humanitarian-learning, arts-based methods, and reflective and dialogical approaches). We will consider how to apply these techniques in various engineering disciplines (civil, mechanical and aerospace, electronic and electrical, chemical, and software) and/or the types of engineering courses the participants teach (e.g., foundational classes on thermodynamics, chemistry, physics, calculus, design).

RIHEEE Ethics Bingo Card #10

Case Studies	Project-Based Learning	Arts-Based Methods	Value-Sensitive Design	Service Learning
14) Electrical Eng. Power Systems	3) Software Eng. Inclusive Tech Design	22) Aerospace Eng. Human Spaceflight Ethics	9) Mechanical Eng. 3D Printing & Bioethics	17) Civil Eng. Affordable Housing Design
7) Chemical Eng. Waste Reduction & Recycling	21) Mechanical Eng. Drones & Public Safety	5) Software Eng. Social Media & Misinformation	13) Electrical Eng. Neural Interfaces	25) Aerospace Eng. Drone Warfare Ethics
19) Civil Eng. Water Resource Management	11) Software Eng. AI Bias in Hiring	1) Mechanical Eng. Exoskeleton Ethics	16) WILD CARD! (Any method, any discipline!)	8) Chemical Eng. Sustainable Packaging
4) Electrical Eng. Facial Recognition & Privacy	24) Civil Eng. Public Transportation Ethics	10) Aerospace Eng. Climate Change & Aviation	20) Mechanical Eng. AI in Manufacturing	2) Software Eng. Predictive Policing & Bias
15) Chemical Eng. Food Engineering & Ethics	12) Mechanical Eng. Smart Prosthetics	18) Electrical Eng. Cryptocurrency & Sustainability	6) Software Eng. Dark Patterns in UX	23) Aerospace Eng. Orbital Debris & Responsibility

Figure 2. Featured outputs of the pilot test from the 2025 SEFI Ethics Spring Symposium, illustrating the range of active learning situations one team discussed.

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